

**THE INTERNAL DYNAMICS OF GULF COOPERATION
COUNCIL: DISINTEGRATING COHESION AMONG THE
MEMBER STATES**

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Abstract:

The Present paper aims to study the disintegrating cohesion within the Gulf Cooperation Council, that had become unmanageable post-2011. Prior to the Arab uprisings, the member-states had collectively and consensually resolved their internal disputes, being one of the most stable organizations in the West Asian region. The reshuffling of regional dynamics following the Arab uprisings, the emergence of new-generational leadership in small-gulf states with assertive policies and decision-making, a diversion is evident within the GCC bloc. These divergence and disagreements among the member-states had fractured the unity and cohesiveness of the Cooperation Council. Qatar has remained a major irritant in the efficient working of the Council. The Qatar-blocade, 2017 was the gravest crisis for the bloc since its formation, that hit at the limitations and weaknesses of institutionalization of the Council. The fragmentation of the Council is a major challenge before the oil monarchies to withhold their unity and cooperation in at a time when the region is undergoing the worst crisis of the century. The GCC need to review its policies, put aside their bilateral rivalries and work on mending the ruptures that are threatening the stability, cooperation and unity of the Council.

Keyword: Gulf region, Cohesion, Disintegration, Regional dynamics, Cooperation

The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) is considered as one of the successful and stable regional groupings in an unstable and volatile West Asian region. In 1981, Bahrain, Kuwait, Qatar, Oman, Saudi Arabia and UAE unanimously agreed on the establishment of GCC to institutionalize the existing unity and cooperation among these six gulf- states. Despite

the ideological differences among the member-states, instabilities and crisis at the regional level, the GCC states had ensured stability and integration in its forty-four years of existence. The recent instances of the disintegrating unity due to the divergence among the member states on various geopolitical matters has emerged as a matter of concern. The present paper aims to study the integration that had bind the GCC states together over the years despite the internal crisis and the events of divergence that had put the grouping at the brink of disintegration.

The first section gives a brief historical overview of the establishment of the GCC in 1981, the basic objectives of the Council and cohesion among the states in the subsequent years. The divergence among within the GCC grouping had been more noticeable since 2010, hence the primary focus of the paper is on the post-2010 period, witnessing a phase of disagreements and widening state-to-state rivalries. The second section of the paper will focus on the events in the post-2010 period, that is the Arab Spring, the Qatar-blocade 2017, the Saudi-UAE rivalry, the Abraham Accords, normalization deals with Israel, and the ongoing war in Gaza. Qatar has remained a major irritant in the efficient working of the Council. The paper will also highlight the challenges of structuring a cohesive security policy. The diverging security perception had further hindered the development of a cohesive defence policy of the Council. The last section discusses the future prospects and challenges of widening divergence that has the potential to cause fragmentation of the Council. The widening divergence is a major challenge before the oil monarchies to withhold their unity and cooperation in the political, economic and security arena at a time when the region is undergoing the worst crisis of the century. The GCC need to review its policies, put aside their bilateral rivalries and work on mending the ruptures that are threatening the stability, cooperation and unity of the Council.

The Establishment of Gulf Cooperation Council

The Cooperation Council of Arab Gulf States or the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), established in 1981 as a regional political and economic organization to promote cooperation among the member states. GCC is considered one of the successful and stable regional groupings in the West Asian region. The discussions on the establishment of a council of Arab gulf began in 1975 and had several meetings in the subsequent years. Due to the lack of consensus on the issues of security, defence and

foreign policy among the eight gulf states, both the meetings ended up without any conclusive agreement (Ulrichsen, 2018). The emerging ideational threats to the gulf monarchies following the Iranian Revolution, and the Iran-Iraq war coalesce the existing idea of establishing a cooperation council of the gulf states and removed the consideration of inclusion of Iran and Iraq in the regional council. The official discussions began in February 1981 with representatives from Bahrain, Kuwait, Qatar, Oman, Saudi Arabia and UAE. And within a few months, the six gulf states officially established the Cooperation Council of the Arab Gulf States, on 25 May 1981. Despite their differences over the structure of the organization, the commonalities among the member states in religion, language, history, economic and political structure consolidated the Council. It was the ideational threats from pan-Islamism of Iran and Iraq's pan-Arabism that united the six gulf states on a common platform for ensuring the stability of the monarchical regimes (Berger, 2014).

The GCC Charter states for, 'co-ordination, integration and inter-connection between member states in all fields to achieve unity between them, to deepen and strengthen relations, links and areas of cooperation' (The Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf, Secretariat General 2024). It explicitly mentions for cooperation in economic, financial, industrial, education and cultural matters, that has ensured cohesion and unity among the member states over the years. However, the member-states insisted that the Council was not a security or political organisation (Ulrichsen, 2018; Barnett and Gause, 1998, p.169). In view of Ulrichsen, many critical issues were left unaddressed due to the speed at which the organization was created, lacking an integrative decision-making institution or any comprehensive military alliance and foreign policy making power (Ulrichsen, 2018). The security issues were not mentioned in the official Charter, rather was slightly mentioned in the section, 'other field' in the Riyadh Communique (Miller, 2016, p.123-124). The security issues found a place in Council's discussion in 1983, but over the years, it has failed to unite the members on the issues of security and defence. The GCC remains a unified yet diverged bloc, the fragmentation seems more apparent since the Qatar blockade, 2017.

GCC as a Unified and Cohesive organization: The areas of Cooperation

The cohesion and cooperation among the member-states has kept the GCC bloc alive, despite the widening divergence. The Supreme Council of the GCC adopted the Unified Economic Agreement at its second session held in November 1981, that includes ‘economic integration through the establishment of the Free Trade Area, the Custom Unions, the Common Market; convergence and unification of laws in financial and trade areas; and interconnecting the infrastructure of the member-states and promoting the establishment of joint ventures’ (The Unified Economic Agreement of the Cooperation Council for the Arab States of the Gulf, 1981). This agreement constituted the core of integration programme adopted in the initial twenty years of the establishment of the Council. In 2002 all the GCC member states implemented the Common Custom Law, followed by establishing the Customs Union in 2003. The announcement of custom union was a prominent shift in the joint economic matters, aiming to liberalize the Intra-GCC trade and allowing the free flow of goods across the member-states. The GCC Common Market was launched in 2008, that aimed at creating one market for raising production efficiency (Low and Salazar, 2015). It further extended equal rights to the citizens of GCC states, to take up employment, residence, education and establish companies in the member states. The progress of the GCC bloc has been more in the technical and apolitical areas (Ulrichsen, 2018), the expansion of technical committees, in the areas of health, education, agriculture had further cohesion of the member-states. Recently, GCC announced a unified tourist visa, ‘GCC Grand Tours’, with a validity of thirty days, it allows the travelers to visit all the six member-countries of the GCC.

The dispute settlement mechanism of the Council, ‘The Commission for the Settlement of Disputes’, mentioned in Article 10 of the GCC Charter, has successfully dealt with the border disputes and the other areas of disagreement among the member-states. Also, the member-states had collectively managed their internal and bilateral disputes prior to 2011, through the mediation of other GCC leaders. Qatari-Saudi border dispute of 1992 was resolved through Oman’s mediation, Saudi mediated in Qatari-Bahraini tensions in 1996, and then Kuwait mediated Saudi-Qatari tensions of 2023 (Heard-Bey, 2006, p.209)

The GCC states exhibited strong cohesion in instances of external threat that threatened the regime stability of the gulf monarchies. As Guzansky noted, ‘the history of the GCC countries has demonstrated, when threats

grew, it proved easier to put their disputes behind and put forth an image of unity' (Guzansky, 2014). During the Iran-Iraq war of 1980s, Iraq invasion of Kuwait in 1990, or the invasion of Iraq in 2003, the GCC states opted for a unified stance. GCC emerged unscathed from these three major wars in the gulf region, because of flexibility in approach that brought consensus on certain issues (Ulrichsen, 2020). The flexibility and pragmatism among the member-states seems to rupture with emergence of new generation of leaders and their assertive and autonomous policies (Ulrichsen, 2020). The response of the six-monarchies to the Arab uprisings, as Ulrichsen says, 'shattered the notion of consensus and constituted the schism that fractured the GCC in 2014 and again in 2017' (Ulrichsen, 2020, p.306). The subsequent section assesses the events of fragmenting consensus and cooperation among the member-states, that hinted at the limitations and weaknesses of the GCC.

The Fragmenting Cohesion in the GCC bloc

Since the establishment of the Gulf Cooperation Council, the divergence among the member-states had been as apparent as the convergence. Though the policy diversions had widened in the post-Arab uprising period, the pro-democracy protests that had shifted the regional balance of power. While the member-states opted for a united stance in events of external threats to the monarchical regimes, the bloc lacks a comprehensive foreign policy. The foreign policy largely remains individual business of the member states, the divergence is more evident with the shifting balance of power in the region. The increasing regional and international influence of the small gulf states, had raise their prominence to play critical role in regional politics. These small states, Oman, UAE, Qatar, Kuwait and Bahrain had become active players in region's politics, that challenged the existing Saudi-centric nature of the Gulf Cooperation Council. These small states become assertive in terms of their policies and decisions that widened the disagreements among the GCC states. In 2009, UAE withdrew from GCC monetary union, a project that was in consideration since long. The reason was shifting the location of GCC central Bank from Abu Dhabi to Riyadh. Then in 2011, the Saudi King proposed for the formation of a Gulf Union, with the inclusion of Jordan and Morocco. Saudi's idea failed comprehensively over Oman's refusal to be a part of any such union.

These events exemplified the dismantling of consensual and collective decision making, that had constituted the very nature of Council.

The imbalance in the structure of the bloc, that constitutes five states of varying smallness and a very large state, constantly wary small member-states of Saudi's growing influence over the Council. GCC was established amidst the growing threats from Iran and Iraq to expand their influence over the gulf region. It was Saudi Arabia the only gulf state, economically and politically in position to lead the five small gulf states. In order to mitigate against the breaking regional balance of power, the small gulf states bandwagon with Saudi Arabia, under the institutionalization of the Gulf Cooperation Council (Ulrichsen, 2021). Saudi's dominant position had developed a fear of Saudi-hegemony among the members, constraining the unity and coherence of the bloc. As Abdullah Baabood stated, Riyadh's reluctance to relinquish dominance is damaging the cohesion of the Council' (Baabood, 2023). The intensifying Saudi-UAE rivalries over economic competition and divergence of interests between had further undermined the integrity of the GCC (Baabood, 2023).

The ruptures in the GCC widened in the post-Arab Spring period, the disagreements became unmanageable. The small states seeking to assert themselves and their distinct identities over the regional politics widened the competition among the member-states (Kamrawa, 2018, p.81-2). The reshuffling of the regional politics after 2011, led a paradigm shift in GCC states regional approach, the states started supporting like-minded governments and organisations through economic and military support (Ulrichsen, 2018). Bahrain, Saudi Arabia and UAE perceives Iranian and Shiite threats as the reason for the regime change and political instability in the region following the Arab Spring and are extremely concerned over being vulnerable to these external threats (Guzansky, 2014; Ulrichsen, 2018). Qatar has opted for cooperation with the Islamist and Iranian Shiite groups, without perceiving any imminent threat to their domestic instability from these forces. Oman and Kuwait to a larger extent remains neutral due to their political and economic position (Tok, 2020). This divergence over threat perception and policies towards regional disruptions, Qatar's growing closeness to Islamist forces developed unfixable ruptures in the Council. It weakened the inherent pragmatism among the member-states over 'collective decision-making and resolving their internal discords through consensus' (Kamrawa,

2018). In view of Ulrichsen, 'the ability of GCC as an institution, to accommodate and absorb the divergent approaches to key regional issues broke down after 2011 (Ulrichsen, 2018, p.312).

In 2014 the bloc had a diplomatic rift, when Saudi Arabia, Bahrain and UAE withdrew their ambassadors to Doha, over the accusations of providing refuge to the members of Muslim Brotherhood that led to political instability in Egypt. However, rift was resolved within some nine months through Kuwaiti mediation. Then in 2017, the GCC was hit by the gravest crisis that highlighted the most severe limitations of the integrative institutionalization of the Council since its establishment. Saudi Arabia, UAE, Bahrain, severed diplomatic ties with Qatar and imposed a land, sea and air blockade on the state. The reason was Qatar's constant linkages with terrorist groups including the Islamist group, Hamas, Muslim brotherhood and Iran. However, Kuwait and Oman didn't join the blockade, instead kept their diplomatic channels open with Qatar. The constant and longstanding policy differences among the GCC states was one of the significant reasons for the Crisis of 2017 (Gengler and Al-Khelaifi, 2019). Mehjoob Zweiri stated 'the crisis-induced rifts in the GCC's social fabric (Gulf Crisis' Third Anniversary, 2020), bringing the bloc just at the brink of disintegration. The rift rendered the bloc irrelevant, although it continued to function throughout the crisis, but the challenges of the blockade were evident during the first GCC summit post-Qatar blockade. The intra-GCC rift ended with the signing of al-Ula agreement in 2021, restoring much needed cohesion to the Gulf Cooperation Council. Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Bahrain, and Egypt lifted blockade imposed on Qatar and restored the diplomatic relations. The Qatar blockade hit heavily on the points of limitations and weaknesses of the Gulf Cooperation Council, that left the six-member organization struggling to regain its relevance (Ulrichsen, 2021).

The Council further suffers from the lack of a comprehensive security and defence policy the security concerns acted as driver for balancing the cohesion of the GCC bloc, however the divergence over security perceptions had widened the fragmentation after 2011. Though security concerns were not mentioned in the GCC Charter, but the regime stability and security of the gulf monarchies was the key consideration that led to the establishment of the GCC bloc. GCC's joint military force, Peninsula Shield of 1984, aimed at defending the member-states from external threats, largely remains irrelevant. Importantly, the

reshuffling of regional dynamics post-2011, had put forth new security challenges for the GCC. The United States diminishing role as the security-guarantor for the gulf, had caused a sort of rethinking among the GCC member-states. However, the diverging threat perceptions, the emerging interplay of Islamist groups in the region's politics, is dividing the bloc in opposite factions, consistently restricting coordinated security efforts in dealing with the regional instabilities. The small-states are concerned over Saudi's security concerns dominating the Council's security policy. While United Arab Emirates (UAE), Bahrain and Saudi Arabia favour a 'collective security process to address the member-states security needs', the small states, Kuwait, Qatar and Oman are more inclined towards 'a cooperative security model that will account for their concerns and regional interests' (Sanam Vakil, 2022). These disagreements and different threat perceptions had limited the development of a comprehensive and collective security policy of the Council.

The outbreak of Gaza war on October 7 to regional escalation with Houthis attacks on the Red Sea had posed another security challenge for the GCC. The war occurred at a time when the GCC monarchies had agreed for normalizing relations with Israel backed by United States, sidelining the Palestine issue. Though, the GCC member-states never had a single position on Israel-Palestine, rather in view of Ulrichsen, 'straddles a spectrum of positions, from no ties with Israel for Kuwait, to Oman, Bahrain and Saudi Arabia having pragmatic coexistence while Bahrain and UAE had opted for full normalisation with Israel (Ulrichsen, 2023). From initial divergence over the war, UAE and Saudi playing a leadership role while Qatar was involved in mediating the Israel-Hamas war through diplomatic negotiations. An understanding has developed among the member-states to deal with the regional crisis unitedly, putting aside their intra-GCC conflicts and disagreements. The council recently adopted the 'Vision for Regional Security' initiative in December, 2024, the explicit mention of the ongoing crisis is Gaza in the document, highlights the collective role of the GCC in resolving the Israel-Palestine conflict and maintaining regional stability and peace.

Conclusions

While the economic cooperation, similar economic and political structure, shared cultural values, common history and security concerns, united the six-Persian Gulf states under the institutionalization of Gulf

Cooperation Council in 1981, the distinct identities and individual specifications of the member-states had caused disintegration in one of the most stable organizations in the West Asian region. The disagreements became unmanageable after 2011, the member-states lacking trust and confidence dismantled the consensual and collective decision making, that constituted the dynamic nature of the Council. GCC had managed their internal crisis either through consensus or the mediation by other member-states. The reshuffling of regional dynamics played a critical role in rupturing the cooperation in the Council, member-states assuming the role on the regional issues consistent with their individual states' interests and unique perceptions. The severe crisis in 2014 and 2017 divided the bloc into factions, highlighting its limitations and weaknesses in fully-functioning as a comprehensive organization. As Abdullah Bishara argued that 'without a leadership, the GCC bloc is like a train of six carriages, without a state to pull it, where Saudi is playing a dominant position that of a big brother' (Partrick, 2011). While Gengler and Kheilaifi noted, 'the small gulf states are reluctant to surrender their sovereignty to an economically dominant Saudi Arabia, that remains a continuous barrier to cooperation' (Gengler and Kheilaifi, 2019, p.400). The personalization of policy-making in the Gulf states, where decisions are taken by small circles of senior members of ruling family has impacted the institutionalization of the Council. The emergence of new generational leadership in Saudi Arabia and UAE is antithetical to the working of first generation's traditional style leadership in Kuwait and Oman (Bianco, 2018). The new and disruptive approach of new leaders of UAE and Saudi Arabia to regional issues, seems to institutionalize the alliance behind their respective ambitions (Bianco, 2018). The Saudi-UAE bilateral partnership initiative, 'Saudi-Emirati coordination council', announced during the Qatar crisis, challenged the inclusive nature of the GCC and hinted at 'the new exclusionary axis in the Gulf-politics' (Ulrichsen, 2018). The regional escalation of ongoing Gaza war, that threatens the security of GCC states had renewed the close ties among the member-states. While GCC has prospects of achieving more through internal cooperation and coordination, it needs to restructure its institutionalization framework, it needs to achieve internal-coherence for developing a united foreign approach, a comprehensive security policy, one that avoid dictation of

personal choices and interests supported by a mechanism to resolve conflicts and achieve coordinated and consensual decision-making.

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